

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PRACTICAL SKILLS IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS BASED ON CLUSTER APPROACH

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Abstract. *In this article, the formation and development of practical skills of elementary school students based on the cluster approach is one of the urgent pedagogical problems of today.*

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People with intellectual potential are independent-thinking, skilled, educated personnel with high human qualities who can ensure modern development of international standards. In independent Uzbekistan, the state policy aimed at forming a new generation of high intellectual potential personnel is being pursued. One of the main tasks carried out in this way is the establishment of a new educational system that will be the basis for the development of independent Uzbekistan. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026 [1] is a clear example of this.

From September 1, 2021, the new National Curriculum will be introduced into the educational process. In the textbooks of this program, special attention is paid to the development of oral speech and logical thinking of students. This, in turn, serves to develop students' intellectual abilities and thereby provide society with educated, potential, and capable human capital[3]

It is appropriate to start the formation and development of practical skills in elementary school students first of all from the family. "When I am asked what is the greatest wealth, an educated, intelligent, polite, thinking child is the greatest wealth of parents.

I would say that it is wealth, - said the first President of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov in his article "The welfare of the family is the welfare of the nation". Such those who have wealth are recognized by the community as rich parents, rich family. Such a family will never be humiliated."

Naturally, no family can achieve such a high position on its own. For this purpose, due to the healthy family environment, great mentoring service of parents, their comprehensive upbringing faithful to the teachings, teachings and traditions of their ancestors, they raise intelligent, cultured, righteous children. can be brought to adulthood. These children are the unique wealth not only of the family, but also of the community, neighborhood and, finally, the nation. That is why, according to historical sources, when asked what is the most complex and at the same time responsible profession and task in the world, parents. It is not for nothing that he answered that it is his job and coaching profession[4]

Today, in order to form practical skills in our children, raising children in families in the spirit of national independence, instilling in them national pride, national consciousness and self-

awareness, feelings of patriotism, instilling the idea of love for the child and the country, the nation and the people. By cultivating a sense of respect for the past and its values, it is possible to create a foundation for deep study of the scientific heritage of our ancestors.

Today's children's formation and development of their practical skills is influenced by the neighborhood factor, which is a national model of self-management - a unique socio-spiritual environment in which the main part of a person's life passes, his thinking, his attitude to life is formed. In our opinion, we must also connect to the factor of existing labor teams. The reason is that the Uzbek family has never lived apart from the neighborhood. The family qualities of the family have always been manifested in the life of the neighborhood. That is, the upbringing of the child in the family is clearly visible in the activities held in the neighborhood. Our children acquire the norms of etiquette in the neighborhood more perfectly. If our educational system is based on the principle of integrity of education and upbringing, the quality of education will be high in the place where well-educated children receive education. In this way, we have taken the first steps to form and develop the practical skills of our children on a cluster basis. The next step is the organization of preschool education. In this place, not only upbringing, but also education is given to children in an integrated manner. It is here that parents should be given another task - the task of cooperating with the preschool education organization in order to facilitate the child's integration into the educational process. The use of parental support will have a positive effect so that the child acquires and consolidates the basic knowledge he receives in kindergarten. In this regard, it can be achieved by explaining and teaching parents that we can use them to educate our children, as a result of the extreme improvement of communication tools and the excessive expansion of communication communications.

In raising a child, the activities of the family, school, and community should be focused on one goal, complement each other, and be mutually cooperative. Only then this activity will give expected results as a whole.

In the family, parents should teach their children the need to learn, that a person can reach the peak of maturity thanks to knowledge. After all, the key to any field is knowledge, intelligence and hard work. If a person diligently acquires knowledge, applies it in practice, sharpens his thinking by thinking, he will definitely achieve his goal. Therefore, our parents should create an opportunity and family environment for their children to study and engage in science. He should be aware of his children's manners at school, their passion for learning, and their interests. Helping parents with their children's tasks in a subject if they can give, it is appropriate to talk about the fact that the child will not ask anything from them next time, he may not want to teach.

Every evening, especially in primary classes, it is necessary to monitor, inquire and help the children's studies. A child who gets used to studying every day will later become accustomed to studying on his own even when control is reduced.

If you want your child to have a bright future only if you get knowledge, whether you are engaged in commerce, whether you become an engineer, a scientist, a doctor or a designer, whether you run a company - for everything you need knowledge, you need thinking, you need intelligence. If he explains that perception is necessary, the child will try to learn and will work for himself.

What do you think a primary school teacher should do to form and develop practical skills of primary school students based on the cluster approach? In our opinion, neighborhood, pre-school education, and school cooperation play an important role in this regard. The elementary school teacher in the general secondary educational institution works in this regard on the basis of

the principle of easy-to-difficult practical skills of the student. should be formed. It is appropriate to teach a first-grade student how to write numbers, and then teach him to perform operations on one-digit numbers in the example of mathematics lessons. By assigning independent tasks to students as homework, the development of the practical skills formed in them is achieved. Handouts, instructional tools and methods used by science teachers with a creative approach are of particular importance in the formation and development of students' practical skills. Examples include:

Didactic game "Silence".

Didactic task: to determine children's understanding of simple counting and strengthening.

The task of the game: to count specific items "in mind" and the required number with fingers show

The course of the game: the teacher acts as a leader.

Teacher:

- Guys, let's play the game "Silence". I have different things for you now I'll show you. You will have to find their number.

The children suddenly burst into conversation.

"No, guys." You must raise your hand before answering.

The teacher lists circles and sticks to the children.

- Now I will show you things. You count without making a sound, you show with your fingers how much it is.

When the teacher shows 4 dolls, all the children show their four fingers shows. Silence in the classroom. All the children's attention is on completing the task directed.

Teacher:

- Congratulations, you all calculated correctly. Now I will take the counting stick from one hand to the other, and you count them without making a sound, and then you will show me how many there are.

Children follow the actions of the teacher, count and 10 fingers they show

Teacher:

"Now count the squares," he says, putting squares on the board one after the other.

Children count and show 6 fingers.

Here is an approximate level of children's knowledge of the first ten is determined by the ability to count on the fingers as many things as are shown is strengthened practically.

In addition, they also have the ability to count "in the mind" without making a sound is formed. Children actually achieve counting without having to repeat it out loud they can't, only the rule of the game requires them to sit quietly, and they count without making a sound. The convenient part of doing this is that the children's entire attention is occupied only with completing the task. In the next lesson, the conditions of the game will be more complicated. Through this game, students' quick movement skills are strengthened. At the same time, it becomes possible to determine who is performing the task quickly and who is slow. This, in turn, helps to determine which students the teacher should be more involved with and which students should involve their parents more in education in which places.

In conclusion, in forming and developing the practical skills of elementary school students based on a cluster approach, as a result of the cooperation of the family, preschool education,

neighborhood and general secondary education organization, a solid foundation is created for the development of the necessary personnel for the society.

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